

Tuning and Amplification in Gecko Auditory Hair Cells

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ABSTRACT

We developed an isolated auditory papilla of the crested gecko to record from the hair cells and explore the origins of frequency tuning. Low-frequency cells displayed electrical tuning, dependent on Ca^{2+} -activated K^+ channels; high-frequency cells, overlain with sallets, showed a variation in hair bundle stiffness which when combined with sallet mass could provide a mechanical resonance of 1 to 6 kHz. Sinusoidal electrical currents injected extracellularly evoked hair bundle oscillations at twice the stimulation frequency, consistent with fast electromechanical responses from hair bundles of two opposing orientations, as occur in the sallets. Evoked oscillations were reduced by lowering Ca^{2+} , but not by block of the mechanotransduction channels by dihydrostreptomycin or salicylate block of prestin. We suggest the phenomenon provides electro-mechanical amplification to augment passive mechanical tuning of the sallets over the high-frequency region.

INTRODUCTION

The structure of the auditory papilla of lizards shows substantial diversity among species (Manley, 2011) with the likely evolutionary drive being to increase the upper frequency limit of hearing beyond the 1 kHz seen in frogs or turtles. The main variation is in the tectorial covering of the sensory hair bundles, which can be continuous, as in the turtle, or a series of discrete tectorial sallets each surmounting a transverse row of bundles, or occasionally completely absent. The morphological arrangement, frequency range and tonotopic organization of lizard auditory papillae has been extensively studied by Geoff Manley and his colleagues; his auditory nerve recordings in the Tokay gecko exhibit a frequency range up to 5 kHz (Manley et al 1999). However, little is known about the electrical properties of the sensory hair cells or their role in frequency tuning. We have developed an isolated preparation of the auditory papilla of the crested gecko, *Correlophus ciliatus*, to address this lack of information.

METHODS

Crested geckos, *Correlophus ciliatus*, were obtained from Tony Gamble (Department of Biology, Marquette University, Milwaukee) and had snout-to-tail lengths of 60-90 mm. Animals were anesthetized with isoflurane and decapitated as approved by the IACUC at the University of Wisconsin-Madison. The auditory papilla was isolated (with the tectorial covering usually removed) and mounted in a recording chamber on a Leica fixed stage microscope with a Hamamatsu CCD camera (Beurg et al 2022); patch clamp electrodes were introduced from the abneural edge of the papilla. The stiffness of a hair bundle was determined by its deflection with a flexible glass fiber, bundle motion being followed by imaging on a photodiode pair (Crawford & Fettiplace 1985). Electrical currents were passed across the papilla from a WPI A395 stimulus isolation unit connected to two extracellular glass electrodes (Beurg et al 2022) one comprising a 3% Agar 3M KCl bridge in contact with a chloridized Ag wire, the other filled with saline.

RESULTS

The length of the auditory papilla was 1.6 ± 0.1 mm, with the basal third covered with a continuous tectorial membrane and the apical two-thirds with sallets, each surmounting a single transverse row of

bundles (Fig. 1). We found that in the non-sallet region, and for at least part of the sallet region, hair cells displayed electrical tuning dependent on Ca^{2+} -dependent K^+ (BK) channels (Fettiplace, 2020). The voltage ringing was abolished by application of 1 mM TEA, known to block BK channels, and 2 mM CoCl_2 , that blocks voltage dependent Ca^{2+} channels. Both manipulations also greatly reduced an outward K^+ current, the amplitude of which increased with resonant frequency. The resonant frequencies were mapped tonotopically with the frequency increasing from base to apex, a polarity opposite to that of most other vertebrates but previously observed for the Tokay gecko (Manley et al. 1999). A feature of the map was that electrical tuning occurred over 70 percent of the papilla, including part of the sallet region (Fig.1).

Figure 1. A. Structure of the gecko auditory papilla. B. Tonotopic organization: electrical resonance (open circles), predicted mechanical resonance of hair bundles (red squares) and auditory nerve recordings in Tokay gecko (blue circles, from Manley et al 1999). Electrical resonant frequencies were corrected to 28°C using a Q10 of 2.0 (Fettiplace, 2020).

We characterized hair bundle morphology along the papilla, in non-fixed papillae under the compound microscope. Our measurements agreed with those previously made on fixed papillae of the Tokay gecko (Authier & Koppl, 1995). Over the sallet region, occupying the apical two-thirds of the papilla, the hair bundle length decreases about three-fold from 16 μm to 5.5 μm , and the stereociliary complement increases in tandem from 28 to 48. Recalling that bundle stiffness is proportional to the stereociliary number and inversely to the square of bundle height (Crawford & Fettiplace, 1985), these two morphological variations predict a 13-fold base-apex gradient in bundle stiffness. Direct experimental measurements of bundle stiffness gave a range from 0.5 to 0.04 mN/m between 0.1 and 0.6 of the distance along the papilla from the apex. The stiffness for radial motion of each sallet when attached to a row of hair bundles is determined by the stiffness of each bundle and the number of bundles affixed to each sallet. The number of bundles increases from about two at the base to five at the apex, thereby boosting the apical (high-frequency) stiffness of the bundle-sallet complex 2.5-fold. Therefore, the stiffness of each complex increases 32-fold (from base to apex, and when coupled with the sallet mass (calculated as 1.9×10^{-12} kg) is expected to provide a passive mechanical resonance for the sallets from 1 to 6 kHz.

The combination of sallet stiffness and mass may confer a passive mechanical resonance on the hair bundle input but this is likely to be overdamped in the absence of local amplification. We investigated

possible electromechanical amplification mechanisms by monitoring motion of individual hair bundles in response to electrical current passed across the epithelium. Sinusoidal trans-epithelial currents at 50 to 800 Hz evoked bundle oscillations, often at twice the frequency. The maximal amplitude of the bundle movements ranged from 10 nm to over 100 nm; the amplitude declined with frequency to half maximum at about 500 Hz, equivalent to a time constant of 0.3 ms.

Figure 2. A. Hair bundle oscillations elicited by 50 Hz, 0.4 mA trans-epithelial current. Responses are at 100 Hz and are largely abolished by reducing Ca^{2+} influx. B. Responses unaffected by 20 mM Na salicylate to block prestin. C. Bundle oscillations in a third cell in response to 200 Hz, 0.2 mA are unaffected by 0.2 mM dihydrostreptomycin (DHS) which fully blocks the mechanotransduction channels.

The voltage-evoked movements were reversibly diminished by lowering extracellular Ca^{2+} from 2.5 mM to 0.2 mM, or by adding 2 mM CoCl_2 , which are known to block voltage-dependent Ca^{2+} channels (Fig. 2A). Voltage-evoked bundle oscillations were unaffected by 0.2 mM dihydrostreptomycin to nullify the mechanotransduction currents (Fig. 2B), or 20 mM Na salicylate block of prestin action. From other experiments, we ascertained that the polarity of the bundle motion corresponded to negative feedback. Thus, positive current which depolarized the hair cell generated a bundle motion away from the kinocilium, towards the shorter edge of the bundle, which would close the mechanotransduction channels. If all hair cells across a row are depolarized equally by the transepithelial current, the differing electrical responses according to bundle orientation can account for the second harmonic response.

Each sallet covers about six hair bundles, the abneural three point away from the papilla edge and the neural three point towards the papilla edge (Fig. 1A). Hair bundles oriented in one direction contribute one phase of the response, while those oriented in the reverse direction respond with the opposite phase. This would be possible if the evoked bundle response is mediated by motion of the epithelial surface of the papilla, the tops of the hair cells, mechanically coupling adjacent cells. However, it could also arise in theory by fluid coupling between neighboring bundles. The possibility of mechanical coupling was investigated by simultaneously observing transverse motion of silica beads affixed to the epithelial surface between adjacent bundles (Fig. 3A). Motion of the beads to transepithelial currents also displayed a second harmonic response of amplitude like the tip of the bundle (Fig. 3B). In Fig. 3A, the bead on the reticular lamina was 2 μm in diameter, much smaller than hair bundle heights of 10- μm at this location. Fluid flow from motion of adjacent bundles is likely to be small near the base of the bundle and probably insufficient to move the bead by the same amount as the tip of the bundle. To assess the physiological quality of the measurements, the extent of depolarization determined from patch clamp recordings was plotted against the size of the transepithelial current (Fig. 3C-E). The extracellular currents employed would depolarize hair cells by less than 40 mV from a resting potential of -50 mV.

Figure 3. A. Three 2- μm silica beads (**b**) on the reticular lamina at the base of the bundles. B. Comparison of hair bundle motion and bead motion for a 50 Hz, 0.6 mA trans-epithelial current. C, D. Patch recordings showing ringing for intracellular (C) and trans-epithelial (D) current steps. E. Hair cell depolarization for extracellular currents.

A feature of the lizard ear is the large spontaneous otoacoustic emissions (SOAEs), seen in the Tokay gecko as peaks of sound emission between 1 and 4.5 kHz, (Manley et al 1996). Up to 15 peaks may be evident regularly spaced at about 250 Hz increments (Gelfand et al 2011). SOAEs are thought to be a manifestation of a process augmenting cochlear performance by active force generation by the hair cells. One type of force production is oscillatory motion of the hair bundle (Crawford & Fettiplace, 1985; Martin et al 2003). While we did not search for SOAEs in the crested gecko, we occasionally saw oscillations of free hair bundles, spontaneous or elicited by current injection through a patch electrode in the isolated preparation (Fig. 4A, 4B). The evoked oscillations were roughly synchronized to oscillations in the membrane potential. The oscillation frequency *in vivo* is likely to be modified by the presence of an overlying sallet and coordination from adjacent bundles under the sallet, and temperature. The oscillation frequency of 260 Hz (Fig. 4C), when corrected to the gecko body temperature, will increase by a factor of two or more to over 500 Hz, but will still be at the low end of gecko SOAEs. Nevertheless, it illustrates a possible mechanism for generating the SOAEs.

Figure 4. Examples of hair bundle oscillations. A. Hair cell response to current injection via a patch electrode showing ringing in the membrane potential and hair bundle. B. Four stretches of bundle motion in same cell. C. Power spectrum of bundle oscillations showing peak frequency 260 Hz. Temp = 21°C.

CONCLUSIONS

We report a mechanism of electro-mechanical amplification in gecko auditory hair cells that originates by tilting of the reticular lamina and upper surface of the hair cells. The process differs from previously proposed amplification mechanisms, involving bundle motion due to adaptation of the mechano-transduction channels (Martin et al. 2003) or prestin mediated somatic contraction of outer hair cells (Dallos et al. 2008). An important feature of our mechanism is that it allows summation of mechanical responses from hair cells pointing in opposite directions (Fig. 4). Deflections of a sallet away from the abneural edge of the papilla will depolarize abneural cells, eliciting bundle motion in the opposite direction towards the abneural edge; sallet deflection in the same direction will hyperpolarize neural cells, again producing motion towards the abneural edge. The direction of the electro-mechanical responses of hair cells of both polarities will be the same under lateral displacement of an overlying sallet. The mechanism, though unknown, may be like that seen in guinea pig vestibular hair cells (Griguer et al. 1993).

Figure 5. Schematic of transverse section of papilla with tectorial sallet covering hair bundles pointing in two opposite directions. (i) Extracellular currents passed across the papilla with sallet removed elicit opposing directions of bundle motion for currents that depolarize the cell, thus accounting for 2F response (ii) For mechano-transduction, receptor potential for bundle deflections ΔX abneural to neural is hyperpolarizing for neural hair cells and depolarizing for abneural cells. (iii) Stimulation of sallet in vivo, combining (i) and (ii), gives reinforcing bundle displacement in the same direction.

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[Pascal Martin] Have you tried to move the hair bundle with a probe and look for motion of the beads on the apical (reticular lamina) surface?

[Robert Fettiplace] We have deflected the bundles on their own or within a sallet with a probe and measured the mechano-transducer current, but we did not simultaneously image the reticular lamina. Direct measurements of the reticular lamina would be interesting and is what we need to take the experiments further.

[Kuni Iwasa] What is the significance of electrical stimulation? Is it physiological

[Robert Fettiplace] It is a way of depolarizing or hyperpolarizing the hair cells en masse. It has nothing to do with being physiological – we are trying to look at the motion if the cells are depolarized or hyperpolarized. This is the same technique applied by Dolores Bozovic and Jim Hudspeth to bundle motion in the frog saccule and is a way of driving the hair bundles.

[Rob Raphael] I am curious if you have heard of the striated organelle that was reported to go from the cuticular lamina by Anna Lysakowski.

[Robert Fettiplace] Yes we have looked at that organelle and done some labeling for it but have no definitive evidence for its involvement.

[Martin Göpfert] What moves the cuticular plate? Is it directly coupled by calcium binding.

[Robert Fettiplace] The work would be complete if we knew that. I think it is calcium entering through voltage-dependent ion channels around the cuticular plate. There are non-muscle myosins in that region and their mutation causes deafness. This is probably not a mammalian cochlea mechanism, but I would like to add that Griguer et al (1993) found a similar phenomenon in vestibular hair cells.

[Pascal Martin] From the geometry of your electrodes, I would assume that the electric field that you generate is horizontal and under those circumstances, there are previous experiments that some cells may tend to move along the field by a process of galvanotaxis, which is not understood. Have you tried to block myosin with blebbistatin?

[Robert Fettiplace] Galvanotaxis would not explain why some cells move in one direction and some in the opposite direction to generate the two-harmonic component. We have done several experiments with blebbistatin, with variable results. Some showed block and some not, but it is a difficult compound to use, and I do not feel confident enough to publish those positive results.

[Stefanie Gutschmidt] The 2:1 resonance observation makes me think "parametric excitation". Could this be linked to the motion of the hair bundles as in an inverted pendulum with base excitation? Or would it be associated with a physiological/bio-chemical parameter that changes periodically? Is the 2:1 frequency ratio exact and constant over the range of 50 to 800 Hz?

The 2:1 frequency ratio is constant to within experimental error over the 50 to 800 Hz range stimulation.

[Robert Fettiplace] The 2:1 response stems in my view from the two sets of hair bundles pointing in opposite directions, each generating a mechanical response 180 degrees out of phase with the other. A figure has been added to the revised manuscript to illustrate this mechanism.

[Dolores Bozovic] Did you try any other MET channel blockers, such as gentamicin, or perhaps sever the tip links with BAPTA? Also, did the effect vanish with time, as the preparation was allowed to run down?

[Robert Fettiplace] We did not try other channel blockers, but we have no reason to believe that dihydrostreptomycin was ineffective, being used at 0.2 mM, over ten-times the half blocker concentration for the gecko MET currents. We usually do not continue recording during run-down of the preparation so we cannot answer. During conversation with Dr Bozovic, we discussed evidence for bundle oscillations that might underlie gecko spontaneous otoacoustic emissions. The revised manuscript now contains recordings of such spontaneous oscillations.

[Geoff Manley] In our 1999 paper on the reversed tonotopy of *Gecko*, we reported that we found no fibers innervating that "tectorial" region, which was confirmed by the 2007 Chiappe et al. study. Were you able to access the hair cells of the tectorial region and make measurements there?

[Robert Fettiplace] We were unable to make mechanical measurements on the hair cells under the curtain because the bundles were optically inaccessible. However, we did a few patch recordings and found them to be electrically resonant. If the same active voltage-evoked mechanism operates in the curtain hair cells, it will reinforce the overall motion of the papilla, even though the cells are not innervated.